

Clinico-Histomorphological Spectrum of TURBT Biopsies of Urinary Bladder Lesions in a Tertiary Care Centre: A Two-Year Retrospective Study

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Abstract

Introduction: The spectrum of diseases that occur in the urinary bladder, range from congenital malformations to inflammatory conditions to neoplasms. Transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) aims at completely resecting all the visible tumors, whenever feasible. This provides histological staging and grading for further management of such cases. This study aims to evaluate the clinico-histopathological features of TURBT biopsies in a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods: This is a retrospective analysis of urinary bladder lesions received in the Department of Pathology, Government Medical College, Srinagar for histopathological examination over a period of 2 years, January 2019 to December 2020. The department received 166 trans-urethral urinary bladder biopsy specimens during this time interval.

Results: In our study most common age group was >61 years with 54/166 patients (32.5%) followed by 51-60 years with 44/166 patients (26.5%). Male to female ratio was 3.15:1. The most common microscopic diagnosis was low-grade papillary urothelial carcinoma 72 cases (43.4%) while the least common microscopic diagnosis was squamous cell carcinoma 01 case (0.60%). While in 154 cases of Neoplastic lesions, there were 72 cases of low-grade papillary urothelial carcinoma, 67 cases of high-grade papillary urothelial carcinoma.

Conclusion: In Indian population, the diagnosed bladder cancer is predominantly urothelial carcinoma with male predominance. Younger patients present with low grade tumors. Early diagnosis is important in the diagnosis of urinary bladder cancer

Keywords: Turbt, Bladder Cancer, Bladder Lesions

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Introduction

The spectrum of diseases that occur in the urinary bladder, range from congenital malformations to inflammatory conditions to neoplasms. Neoplastic as well as non-neoplastic diseases of the urinary bladder both are quite common. Urothelial carcinoma of urinary bladder cancer is the fourth most common cancer in men and eighth most common malignancy in women in the Western world.[1]

As per the Indian cancer registry data in men, bladder cancer is the ninth most common cancer accounting for 3.9% of all cancer cases.[2] Transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) aims at completely resecting all the visible tumors, whenever feasible. This provides histological staging and grading for further management of such cases.

Aim

This study aims to evaluate the clinico-histopathological features of TURBT biopsies in a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective analysis of urinary bladder lesions received in the Department of Pathology, Government Medical College, Srinagar for histopathological examination over a period of 2 years, January 2019 to December 2020. The department received 166 trans-urethral urinary bladder biopsy specimens during this time interval. The patient information and details of the specimens were recorded for age, sex and histopathological diagnosis. H&E slides were reviewed and findings noted, wherever required.

Results

166 TURBT specimens received in the department of pathology during a period of two years from January 2019 to December 2020 were studied. In TURBT biopsies analysed, a spectrum of different pathological lesions was observed in the study. In our study most common age group was >61 years with 54/166 patients (32.5%) followed by 51-60 years with 44/166 patients (26.5%), 41-50 years with 40/166 patients (24.1%), and least common age group was

< 40 years with 28/166 (16.9%). Male to female ratio was 3.15:1 (Table 1). In the present study, total cases of inflammatory lesions were 10 (6.02%) while 02 (1.20%) cases of metaplastic lesions were noted and neoplasia was present in 154 (92.73%) cases. The most common microscopic diagnosis was low-grade papillary urothelial carcinoma 72 cases (43.4%) while the least common microscopic diagnosis was squamous cell carcinoma 01 case (0.60%). Other microscopic diagnosis under Inflammatory lesions category were chronic non-specific cystitis with 08 cases and malakoplakia with 02 cases. In Metaplastic lesions category, 02 cases of cystitis cystica glandularis were seen. While in 154 cases of Neoplastic lesions, there were 72 cases of low-grade papillary urothelial carcinoma, 67 cases of high-grade papillary urothelial carcinoma, 11 cases of papilloma, 03 cases of PUNLMP and 01 case of squamous cell carcinoma as shown in Table 2 ; (Figure 1 to Figure 4). The age and gender distribution in all the urinary bladder lesions shown in Tab

Table 1: Socio-demographic variables in TURBT specimens

Variable	Number of cases	Percentage
AGE GROUP		
≤ 40 years	28	16.9 %
41- 50 years	40	24.1 %
51- 60 years	44	26.5 %
≥ 61 years	54	32.5%
GENDER		
Male	126	75.9 %
Female	40	24.1 %

Table 2: Distribution of urinary bladder lesions

DIAGNOSIS	Number of Cases	Percentage
INFLAMMATORY		
Chronic non-specific cystitis	08	4.8 %
Malakoplakia	02	1.2 %
METAPLASTIC		
Cystitis cystica glandularis	02	1.2 %
NEOPLASTIC		
Papilloma	11	6.6 %
PUNLMP	03	1.8 %
Low Grade Urothelial Carcinoma	72	43.4 %
High Grade Urothelial Carcinoma	67	40.4 %
Squamous Cell Carcinoma	01	0.6%

*WHO/ISUP – 2016

Table 3: Frequency of urinary bladder lesions with age and gender

Diagnosis (Lesions)	Age Group							
	≤40 years		41-50 years		51-60 years		≥61 years	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
INFLAMMATORY								
Chronic non-specific cystitis	-	-	02	01	02	03	-	-
Malakoplakia	-	01	01	00	-	-	-	-
METAPLASTIC								
Cystitis cystica glandularis	01	-	01	00	-	-	-	-
NEOPLASTIC								
Papilloma	03	00	04	00	01	01	02	00
PUNLMP	-	-	02	00	01	00	-	-
LowGrade Papillary Urothelial Carcinoma	08	04	11	06	18	01	17	07
HighGrade Papillary Urothelial Carcinoma	09	02	08	04	11	05	23	05
Squamous Cell Carcinoma	-	-	-	-	01	00	-	-

Figure 1: Papillary urothelial neoplasm of low malignant potential(PUNLMP). (H&E, 10x)

Figure 2: Low grade papillary urothelial carcinoma. (H&E, 10x)

Figure 3: Low grade papillary urothelial carcinoma showing papillae with mild pleomorphism of cells and maintained basal polarity. (H&E, 40x)

Figure 4: High grade urothelial carcinoma with muscle invasion. (H&E, 10X)

Discussion

Urinary bladder neoplasms are one of the leading causes of cancer related deaths. The incidence of bladder cancer have marked geographic and clinicopathological variation worldwide and it increases with age with cases rising progressively in 6th and 7th decade of life with male predominance.[3] In India, population based studies in different cities and states have placed bladder cancer in top ten malignancies especially in males.[4-8] In our study male:female ratio was 3.15:1 which was correlated with Pudasaini *et al.*[9] (3.5:1) and was lower than Laisharam *et al.*[2] (4.7:1) and higher than Volkan sen *et al.*[10] (1.5:1) and also Gupta *et al.*[11] which state that male preponderance was more common in Indians than other races.[3] Higher incidence in males may be due to differences in smoking habits and occupational exposure.[11-13] In this study, most common age group was >61 years with 32.53% cases which was correlated with studies by Vaidya *et al.*[14] Goyal VK *et al.*[15] Laishram *et al.*[2] The present study result shows that urothelial carcinomas are more common (83.7 %) among the other carcinomas of urinary bladder cancers in this study which is nearly correlated with the study of Goyal VK *et al.*[15] and Sathya *et al.*[3] In our study the low grade urothelial carcinomas

(72 cases) are more compared to the incidence of high grade carcinomas (67 cases). These findings go with the findings of Koyuncher *et al.*[16] as 85 cases for low grade and 40 cases for high grade. The study indicates that the incidence of low grade tumors are more in males (54 cases) than in females (18 cases) with the incidence peak is in the age group of 51-60 years in case of males and 41-50 in case of females. Also the study reveals, the high grade tumors were more common in males compared to females. In this study, 51 cases of males are observed with high grade tumor whereas 16 cases of females with high grade tumor. Among males, the high grade tumors are of peak in the age group of >61 years (23 cases) which goes with the study of Panchal Jaimin *et al.*[17] and Sathya *et al.*[3] In our study muscle invasion was seen in 57.5% cases of urothelial carcinoma (Table 4) which was correlated with Shah *et al.*[18] whose result showed muscle invasion in 69% cases while lamina propria invasion in our study was seen in 75.5% cases of urothelial carcinoma which was correlated with Sathya *et al.*[3] whose results showed lamina propria invasion in 87% case. (Table 5)

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to invasion

Invasion	Present	Absent
Lamina Propria	105(75.5%)	34(24.5%)
Muscularis Propria	80(57.5%)	59(42.5%)

Table 5: Correlation of Distribution of Cases of urothelial carcinoma According to muscle Invasion

Study	Grade	Present	Absent
Present	High Grade	62	05
	Low Grade	18	54
Vaidya [14]	High Grade	76.92%	23.08%
	Low Grade	16%	84%
Goyal Vk [15]	High Grade	82.75%	17.24%
	Low Grade	25.80%	74.19%

This study showed 83.8% pure urothelial carcinoma cases, 0.6% Squamous differentiation cases which was nearly correlated with study of Billis et al.[19], which showed (92.72%) were conventional urothelial carcinomas and 7.27% showed squamous and glandular differentiation. Also in our study there were 4.8 % cases with chronic non specific cystitis which was similar to Goyal VK et al[15] and lower than Vaidya et al.[14] Detection of muscle invasion is of paramount importance because of its influence on therapy and prognosis.[20] Muscle invasion was more in high grade (92.5%) than low grade (25%) urothelial papillary carcinoma. Similar findings were found by Goyal VK et al[15] Vaidya S et al[14] Laishram et al[2].

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